

School-Based Management Practices and Delivery Services Among Selected Secondary Schools in Region XII

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the School-Based Management (SBM) practices as employed by all mega-large secondary schools in Region XII through Key Performance Indicators and Documents, Observations, and Discussions, and established a significant relationship between these practices to the delivery services such as achieving the vision, mission, goals and objectives, students' services, library services, guidance and counseling services, clinic services, laboratory services, curriculum and instruction, community involvement, physical plant and facilities, administration and linkages with stakeholders. This study utilized a descriptive-evaluative design where SSLG, SGC, and SBM principal leaders served as the respondents. The Department of Education's SBM assessment tool and a validated survey questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale were used. Data were analyzed using mean, ANOVA, and Pearson's r . Findings

revealed that the performance of mega-large secondary schools in Region XII in SBM was interpreted as best practices, while the services offered by the school were excellently delivered. Moreover, there was no significant difference in the SBM level of practices; however, in the delivery services, only the South Cotabato and Cotabato Divisions were identified to have substantial differences, and the rest didn't differ. However, there was no significant relationship between the SBM level of practices and delivery services. It was concluded that the SBM level of practices has nothing to do with schools' performance in delivery services. Thus, it was recommended that SBM practices and delivery services be sustained for better school operations with the help of internal and external stakeholders. After all, a bright future is honed in school.

Keywords: *School-Based Management, delivery services, key performance indicators*

INTRODUCTION

School-Based Management (SBM) establishes an outline that administers and offers clear roadmap on educational guidelines and ideals for primary education (Obias, 2023). SBM gives school stakeholders such as principals, teachers, students, and parents control over the education procedure by giving them the duty of making decisions about the budget, employees, and the program. It is a standard of education that allows schools to be independent within the national education framework. Autonomy is given so that schools can manage the resources and funds by allocating them according to local needs (Rizky et al., 2018). The chief purpose for School-Based Management is the upgrading of educational processes and outcomes and implemented as policies for major educational change to address learners' needs in the 21st century (Oester, 2023).

However, Rint, et. al. (2024) noted that the one of the major concerns of the many schools in the Philippines are facing challenges in the preparing learning become competent. Thus, this specific challenge urged teachers to find and implement fitted teaching strategies that may cater learners' unique background and situation. Moreover, schools have also reported that some of the key aspects of the program have not been implemented properly. More so, the shift from the 10-year Basic Education Curriculum to the K-12 Curriculum to the Matatag Curriculum brought many changes in secondary schools. With the advent of the K-12 curriculum, Bala (2017) noted issues with teachers' knowledge of recent pedagogy, education research, monitoring and evaluation, and classroom management. In addition, there are many schools that their external stakeholders do not visit; therefore, tapping the stakeholders is needed. On the contrary, tapped stakeholders are hesitant to show off, for they do not know their roles and responsibilities as school stakeholders (Pepito et al., 2019).

Furthermore, in Beneyat-Dulagan, et. al. (2023) study on the most pressing problems of the most libraries in the Philippines are summarized into limited number of reference books, poor internet connection for searching/browsing, no up-to-date book collections and inadequate facilities. These issues make the library non-accommodating to the needs of the library users. While schools must have guidance counselors, DepEd has only 1,096 active guidance counselors, which comprised 20% of the vacant positions due to low salaries (Magsambol & Chi, 2020). On health services matters in public schools, former DepEd Undersecretary for Administration Alain Del Pascua urged the need for permanent clinics for public schools in the Philippines. He noted that there are only 13,081 clinics, or 28% of the total 47,013 public schools in the country (Hernando-Manlipot, 2020). Thus, giving learners medical attention, such as first aid services, is hampered.

Lastly, secondary public schools also face a lack of sufficient classrooms. One of the schools with an increasing number of students yearly is Sto. Nino National High School struggled with classroom shortages in the School Year 2023-24. In this scenario, each Grades 7-12 classroom holds classes with an average of 60 students. Summing up, Tomacruz (2023) of Rappler Philippines reported that students and teachers welcomed the school year 2023-2024 with classroom shortages.

With these issues in the implementation of SBM, this study was conducted to determine the School-Based Management (SBM) practices of all secondary mega-large schools in Region XII and the relationship of their practices to the delivery of services. While SBM practices are a good measurement of a school's access, quality, and efficiency, it is also right to assess delivery services among secondary mega-large schools after being validated at SBM Level III. After all, consistency in the delivery of services deserves autonomy in the budget allocation from the Department of Budget and Management (DBM).

Theoretical Framework

The implementation of the SBM is a mandate to all public schools in the Department of Education as it is outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, series of 2012 or otherwise known as the Revised School-Based Management (SBM) Framework, Assessment Process, and Tool (APAT). This emphasizes the importance of learners and aims to improve their learning experience. However, its implementation may be challenged by external factors during program operation.

Anchored to the Theory of Equifinality of Ludwig Von Bertalanffy, this theory explains that the process of implementation of SBM may vary from one school to another but same end state should not be sacrificed (Priz, 2022). In this case, implementation of SBM in the Department of Education is affected by the size of the school and geographical location. The size of the school greatly affects SBM implementation. The SBM program entails number of principle and indicators' leaders. Roughly, the program needs more or less 36 faculty and staff to lead each of the principles and indicators. Thus, a school with 36 faculty is considered medium school. Now, how could small school schools implement the program when they have only less 10 faculty? Geographical location of the school may also affect implementation of the program. Schools in geographically isolated and disadvantage areas (GIDA) hardly implement the program for there are many resources needed in the implementation such as the SBM showroom where documents needed for evaluation and validation are displayed. In running the programs entails monetary requirement for apparatuses like computers and printers are the ones important in the production of proof and evidence. With this, how could these GIDA schools properly implement if they could hardly provide needed resources for SBM display, documentation and production equipment? Though schools may face challenges in the implementation of the program, DO 8, s. 2012 do not provide any evasion of implementation but mandates them still to implement the program.

Furthermore, humans are social beings. They thrive to exist in a group where social interaction is structurally connecting with others in a certain society. As young human, he dependent on others and as he grows through a process become adult, be socially dependent on connection and relationship with other (Parkhurst, et. al., 2021). Anchored to the Social cultural Theory of Development of Lev Bigotsky, implementation of SBM does not only rely on the concerted effort of the faculty and staff of the academe but including all the concern internal and external stakeholders of the school. Remember, school can't exist without the help of the society but a society can live without the school. To emphasize more on this theory in relation to the implementation of SBM, each of its indicators of the four principles needs stakeholders such as student, teacher, School-Governing Council or the Parents-Teachers Association. These mentioned personages are insatiable in the conduct of face to face evaluation. Moreover, preparing SBM documents needed for evaluation photo, activity design, such as Learning Action Cell conferences, Triangulation and others that need people in the collection of the documents. With these matters, it only suggests and explains that SBM implementation rely on social interaction and social relation. The program does not work in a limited group of people but multitude of stakeholders with one common vision for the school. They may have gifted with unique talents and skills that contributed to the uniqueness of their personality but through proper channeling of the common goal. Desired outputs are an inch away from success.

Lastly, while SBM is a no one-man program implementation but with multitude of individuals with shared visions for the school which learners are its main clientele. Thus, Decentralization Theorem is another theory to propose distribution of tasks from different fields or principles. This theory was built from early public economics literature from the works of Arrow (1970), Musgrave (1959) and Samuelson (1954; 1955). In relation to SBM implementation, this theory mobilizes large group of individuals with specific functions to accomplish as part of the whole requirement to effectively and efficiently carry out the program.

Limitations of the Study

This study focused on determining the SBM level of practices of mega-large secondary school, particularly those that have already undergone regional validation by the Region XII validators. SBM level of practices focused only on mega large secondary schools' KPIs such as access, quality, and efficiency and DODs on Principle 1: Leadership and Governance, Principle 2: Curriculum and Instruction, Principle 3: Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Principle 4: Management of Resources. Furthermore, this study can also find the relationship of SBM level of practices to their delivery services such as achieving vision, mission, goals and objectives, students' services, library services, guidance counseling services, clinic services, laboratory services, curriculum and instruction, community involvement, physical plant and facilities, administration and linkages with stakeholders. This study was conducted in the School Year 2024-2025 to a total of 495 respondents composed of five (5) major officers of Secondary School Learners Government, five (5) major officers of the School Governing Council, one (1) School-Based Management school coordinator and four (4) School-Based Management principle leaders.

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the SBM level of practices of secondary schools in Region XII regarding delivering services to their stakeholders. It was sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of SBM Practices based on key performance indicators (KPI) and documents, observations, and discussions (DOD) among selected secondary schools in Region XII?
2. What is the level of delivery services among mega large secondary schools in Region XII in terms of:
 - 2.1 achieving vision, mission, goals, and objectives;
 - 2.2 students' services;
 - 2.3 library services;
 - 2.4 guidance and counseling services;
 - 2.5 clinic services;
 - 2.6 laboratory services;
 - 2.7 curriculum and instruction;
 - 2.8 community involvement;
 - 2.9 physical plant and facilities;
 - 2.10 administration; and
 - 2.11 linkages with stakeholders?
3. Is there a significant difference in the SBM Practices employed by the mega-large secondary schools in Region XII?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII?
5. Is there a significant relationship between SBM Practices and the level of delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-evaluative design to assess the SBM level of practices of the mega-large secondary schools in Region XII regarding their delivery services. According to Arifin (2010), descriptive-evaluative research is a design that aims to provide information for program implementers related to the strength of a program like SBM, as noticed from its effectiveness and cost.

Respondents of the Study

Respondents were important for providing responses needed in gathering important data for interpretation and analysis. There were three (3) groups of respondents in this study. These were the key officials in the operation of SBM. Similar to the SBM evaluation either online or face-to-face, the five (5) major officers of SGC (School Governing Council), five (5) major officers of SSLG (Supreme Secondary Learner Government), four (4) SBM principal leaders and one (1) SBM performance indicators leader. Fifteen (15) respondents were purposively chosen to answer the survey questionnaire.

Sampling Technique

The study utilized purposive sampling where respondents were the key officials of the school's SGC, SSLG, SBM principle and key performance indicators leaders. This sampling technique was used to conduct the study, like an SBM evaluation and validation. Moreover, this technique was used to minimize the cost and time required to perform the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before distributing survey questionnaires, the researcher obtained permit from the SKSU GS to conduct a study. Since his committee members signed this form, this is one way of informing them that the researcher is now ready to conduct his study. Since the study's scope was region-wide, permission from the Department of Education, Regional Director of Region XII was sought in order for the researcher to move forward towards accomplishing this study.

After the approval of the letter in the regional office of the Department of Education, another permits to conduct were sought from the offices of the Schools Division Superintendent. Since all mega-large secondary schools in the field have their respective division office, the school division Superintendent should be informed of the conduct of the study. Their approval served as the passport to all the identified mega-large schools in each division. Moving forward, the DepEd Regional Director and Schools Division Superintendent's approval bears or proves the legitimacy of the conduct of the study. Presenting the letter to the school heads was easy when partnered with an approved regional and division letter. As he affixed his signature over the printed name of the letter, the researcher prepared bundled and segregated questionnaire which were also collected after a week. Accomplished survey questionnaires were collected by the school heads. That is why the researcher retrieved the questionnaire easily. Finally, interpreting data is based on the results treated with a statistical tool. These data served as the findings presented and analyzed statistically. They are important because they were used in drawing conclusions and endorsing recommendations.

Statistical Treatment

The discussion of statistical treatment was based on the statement of the problem.

The mean was used to analyze the level of school-based management practices of mega-large secondary schools in Region XII regarding key performance indicators, documents, observations, and discussions.

The mean was utilized to determine how the different respondents assess the level of delivery services of mega-large secondary schools in Region XII in terms of achieving vision, mission, goals and objectives, students' services, library services, guidance and counseling services, clinic services, laboratory services, curriculum and instruction, community involvement, physical plant and facilities, administration, and linkages with stakeholders.

ANOVA was used to determine whether there is a significant difference in the School-Based Management Practices employed by the mega-large secondary schools in Region XII.

ANOVA was used to analyze whether there is a significant difference in the level of delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII.

Pearson's *r* was used to determine the significant relationship between School-Based Management Practices and the level of delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Level of School-Based Management Practices Among Selected Secondary Schools in Region XII

Indicators Descriptive	KPI	DOD	Total	SBM	
	(60%)	(40%)		Rating	Rating
1.South Cotabato Division	55.07	36.16	91.22	2.74	Best
2.Koronadal City Division	55.50	34.90	90.40	2.71	Best
3.Tacurong City Division	53.10	34.20	87.30	2.62	Best
4.Sultan Kudarat Division	52.51	35.66	88.17	2.65	Best
5.Sarangani Division	54.30	36.27	90.57	2.72	Best
6.Gensan City Division	54.24	36.00	90.24	2.71	Best
7.Kidapawan City Division	54.00	36.80	90.80	2.72	Best
8. Cotabato Province Division	54.16	34.90	89.06	2.67	Best
Grand Mean	54.11	35.61	89.72	2.69	Best

Table 1 presents the level of School-Based Management practices among selected secondary schools in Region XII. Based on the existing revised SBM assessment tool of the Department of Education (DepEd, 2012), advanced practices are labeled to schools whose score during the validation of the SBM Region XII validators when reached 2.50-3.00. Undeniably, all the schools under the eight (8) division offices validated by the region as SBM Level III got an individual mean score with the same descriptive rating of advanced. It can be observed that the Koronadal City Division had the highest KPI, which comprised 60% of the total score, while the Sultan Kudarat Division had the lowest. On the other hand, Kidapawan City Division got the highest DOD, which comprised 40% of the total rating; however, Tacurong City Division got the lowest. Though all school divisions in the region have advanced levels of practice regarding SBM, the South Cotabato Division achieved the highest SBM rating. This result was due to one hundred passing rate of the SBM validation conducted by the region in the year 2022. In contrast, Tacurong City Division garnered the lowest. This result may have been affected by the poor division performance on the utilization, monitoring and reporting of the support funds for the implementation of Alternative Learning System (ALS) in School-Based Management in the School Year 2020-21. This had given birth to through DO 21 series 2021 or Implementing Guidelines on the Release, Utilization, Monitoring and Reporting of Program Support Funds for the Pilot Implementation of Inclusion of Alternative Learning System in School-Based Management. The main purpose of the directive was to improve school management and administrative processes particularly advocacy and education campaign for internal and external ALS stakeholders (DO 21, S. 2021). However, the result still suggests that the selected mega large secondary schools in Region XII have satisfying quality standards of practices and procedures for implementing SBM.

In the study of Compendio et al. (2020), the benefits of knowing the organization's mission, vision, goals, and objectives generated the information needed to enhance the institution's practices.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Delivery Services Among Mega Large Secondary Schools in Region XII

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation
1. Achieving Vision, Mission Goals and Objectives	4.26	Services are excellently delivered
2. Students' Services	4.23	Services are excellently delivered.
3. Library Services	4.21	Services are excellently delivered.
4. Guidance and Counseling Services	4.28	Services are excellently delivered
5. Clinic Services	4.21	Services are excellently delivered.
6. Laboratory Services	4.28	Services are excellently delivered.
7. Curriculum and Instruction	4.28	Services are excellently delivered.
8. Community Involvement	4.28	Services are excellently delivered.
9. Physical Plants and Facilities	3.99	Services are well-delivered
10. Administration	4.33	Services are excellently delivered.
11. Linkages with Stake	4.28	Services are excellently delivered.
Grand Mean	4.24	Services are excellently delivered

Table 2 summarizes the level of delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XI. The mean scores in the table are reflections of the services offered by the mega large secondary schools in the region. The result is the totality of the different services that the external and internal stakeholders of the school experience. It was underscored in the table that from the series of mean scores, the administration got the highest mean score of 4.33 with an interpretation of excellently delivered services. This is an output of the school heads who are visionary thinkers who foresee needs in the future and plan effectively, empathetic leaders who consider the individual needs of the leaders, faculty, and staff, and decisive principals who make timely and reasonable decisions that benefit the school, school leaders with high integrity who uphold high moral and transparency and adaptable leaders who sincerely respond to change education set up and challenges in administration arena. At the same time, physical plants and facilities got the lowest mean score of 3.99, interpreted as well-delivered services. Considering the variables in this delivery service, it was noted that the lack of enough classrooms contributed to the achievement of the lowest mean score. Rappler.Com Philippines (2025), the issue of classroom shortage may take 20 years to resolve, considering the 24B budget in the present year. Currently, the Department of Education lacks 165,443 classrooms all over the country. As such, different Regional Offices practice double shift classes, triple shift classes, and a combination of both classes to mitigate the issue. In 2024, the DepEd Learners Information System or LIS reported that Region IV-A adopts triple-shift classes. A total of 64 schools adopted the triple shift classes out of 712 schools in the regions, which was followed by Region VII, which has 27 schools that adopted the triple shift classes out of 238 schools, 14 schools for Region III of the 210 total schools, 12 schools in Region V out of 69 schools, 10 schools in NCR out of 476 schools, while three schools in Region VI and X out of 93 and 76 schools respectively and one school in Region XI out of 117 schools. In the case of other Regions, they adopt double shift classes. Specifically, one of the schools in Region XII, particularly Koronadal National Comprehensive High School, adopted the double shift classes to cater to all its learners, from juniors to seniors.

In contrast, some schools have not adopted double-shift classes. There are schools in Sto. Nino District and Banga District did not implement the double-shift classes. Considering that the classroom size must be a maximum of 45 students, some schools in the said district cannot implement the mandate due to insufficient classrooms. That is why classes have more than 45 students.

Furthermore, administration became the most excellently delivered service by the mega-large schools in Region XII because this is a product of the successful administration of the school heads who have effective leadership, strategic communication, and comprehensive planning, while physical plants and facilities got the lowest mean score. This results from the increasing population and intensive recruitment of learners to enroll or return to school through implementing the DepEd's Education for All (EFA) Program. Getting the average score of all the means resulted in a grand mean score of 4.24, which described all services of the mega-large secondary schools in the region as excellently delivered.

Thus, this only suggests that mega-large secondary schools in Region XII deliver excellent delivery services. Therefore, three consecutive years of being validated by the region as SBM Level III will have autonomy over the School Improvement Plan budget.

Table 3. Results of the ANOVA for Comparison of School-Based Management Practices as Employed by the Mega Large Secondary Schools in Region XII

Sources of Variation	DF	SS	MS	Comp. F (0.05)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Between							
Column	7	49.79	7.11	0.60	0.75	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Within							
Column	25	294.59	11.78				

The table shows the results of the ANOVA for comparison of School-Based Management practices as employed by the mega-large secondary schools in Region XII. The table displays the variables explaining the wisdom behind the study's data. The column has 7 degrees of freedom, a sum square of 49.79, and a mean square of 7.118, while the within column has 25 degrees of freedom, a sum square of 294.59, and a mean square of 11.78. Analysis revealed an f-computed value of 0.60 with a probability of 0.75, greater than $\alpha = 0.05$. There is enough evidence to claim that the difference among means is attributed to chance. The result implies that all mega-large secondary schools may likely have the same level of School-Based Management practices.

According to the results of the study by Badafal et al. (2021), implementing School-Based Management greatly affects teachers' work motivation and school quality. Though implementation of School-Based Management rests for quite some time, service delivery should continue to be practiced as this is the heart of school operation for the betterment of the school community.

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Delivery of Services Among Mega Large Secondary Schools in Region XII

Sources of Variation	DF	SS	MS	Comp. F (0.05)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Between Column	7	1.59	0.23	4.60	<0.0001	Reject Ho	Significant
Within Column	487	23.57	0.05				

The table above clearly explains the significant difference in the delivery of services among mega-large secondary schools in the region. It can be gleaned that the column has 7 degrees of freedom, a sum square value of 1.59, and a mean square value of 0.23, while the column has 487 degrees of freedom, a sum square value of 23.57, and a mean square value of 0.05. It resulted in a computed f-value of 4.60. The analysis showed an f-computed value of 4.60 with a p-value of <0.0001, which is too small compared to $\alpha=0.05$. Evidence is enough to claim that the difference in the means of rating the delivery services is greater than expected by chance. The result implies that at least one of the schools has different delivery services.

Table 5. Separation of Means Using Turkey-Kramer Multiple Comparison Test in the Delivery Services Among Mega Large Secondary Schools in Region XII

Indicators	Means
South Cotabato Division	4.23 ^{bc}
Koronadal City Division	4.34 ^{ab}
Tacurong City Division	4.35 ^a
Sultan Kudarat Division	4.15 ^b
Sarangani Division	4.24 ^{bc}
Gensan City Division	4.24 ^{bc}
Kidapawan City Division	4.33 ^{ab}
Cotabato Province Division	4.24 ^{bc}

Note: Means with common superscripts are comparable

Table 5 details the separation of means using the Turkey-Kramer multiple comparison test in the delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII. This table discusses the comparability and contrast of delivery services among school divisions in Region XII. It can be observed in the table that mean ratings of the mega-large schools in the Divisions of South Cotabato, Koronadal City, Tacurong City, Sarangani Province, General Santos City, Kidapawan City, and Cotabato City exhibited excellent delivery of services. However, the results of the Turkey-Kramer multiple comparison tests revealed that the schools in Tacurong City Division obtained the highest rating of means, comparable to the delivery services of mega-large secondary schools in Koronadal City and Kidapawan City Divisions. At the same time, the mega-large secondary schools in South Cotabato, Sarangani Province, General Santos City, and Cotabato Province may likely have the same delivery service levels. They are comparable to the mega-large secondary schools in Koronadal City and Kidapawan City. Sultan Kudarat Division has a very satisfactory rating, which differs from other mega-large schools in Region XII.

Cuisu (2020) emphasizes that although mega-large secondary schools have 51 or more teachers, performance in the delivery services may vary depending on the location, teachers' expertise and skills, availability of resources, and other external community factors.

Table 18. Relationship Between School-Based Management Practices and Delivery of Services Among Mega Large Secondary Schools in Region XII

Indicators	Mean	r ²	Interpretation
SBM Practices	2.69	0.0492	Weak Positive Correlation
Delivery Services	4.24		

The table presents the significant relationship between School-Based Management Practices and the delivery of services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII. The relationship between the level of School-Based Management practices and the level of delivery services is derived from the ANOVA for classifying services according to the rating of the mega-large secondary schools in the different divisions. The result redounds to the idea that difference among means is caused by School-Based Management practices other than chance. Thus, the overall effect of the SBM practices on the level of delivery services is calculated to obtain $r^2=0.0492$. The result indicates that around 4.92% of the variation of ratings on delivery services is attributed to SBM practices.

Although technically there is a positive correlation, the relationship between the two (2) variables is weak. Note that the r^2 is near to zero (0), the weaker the relationship. With this r^2 , the researcher decided to interpret that there is a weak positive linear correlation between School-Based Management Practices and the delivery of services. It only suggests that when a mega-large secondary school performs best in SMB practices, performance in delivery services may not follow. In other words, performance results in SBM and delivery services are not dependent on each other. Evaluation and validation in SBM practices are done through proper documentation, while delivery services are the actual performance felt and experienced by its stakeholders.

Based on the presentation of data in Chapter IV, the level of School-Based Management practices among selected secondary schools in Region XII got an average score of 2.69, which was interpreted as best level of practices. In terms of delivery services such as achieving vision, mission, goals, and objectives, students' services, library services, guidance counseling services, clinic services, laboratory services, curriculum and instruction, community involvement, administration, and linkages with stakeholders got individual mean scores that have a descriptive rating of excellently delivered services where administration got the highest mean score of 4.33. In contrast, physical plants and facilities got the lowest mean score of 3.99, with a descriptive rating 3.99. The overall rating of the delivery services of the mega large secondary schools in Region XII is 4.24, which describes the delivery services as excellently delivered. It was also found that Region XII's school division performance in implementing School-Based Management marked the same. On the other hand, most of the school's divisions excellently delivered services to their clientele, but services are poorly delivered in terms of physical plants and facilities. Lastly, school division performance in School-Based Management practices was not dependent on performance in delivery services or vice versa.

CONCLUSION

Based on the summary of findings, it was concluded that there is no significant difference in the implementation of School-Based Management practices as in the results of ANOVA for comparison as employed by the mega large secondary schools in the region. However, it revealed a significant difference in the delivery services offered by the mega-large secondary schools. Therefore, the researcher moved further to find out where the substantial difference in the delivery services lay through the separation of

means using the Turkey-Kramer Multiple Comparison Test. Tacurong City, Koronadal City, and Kidapawan City Divisions have comparable delivery service results, while South Cotabato, Sarangani Province, General Santos City, and Cotabato Province Divisions have comparable delivery service results. However, Sultan Kudarat is very different from other mega-large secondary schools in the region. Lastly, this study found a weak positive linear correlation between School-Based Management practices and delivery services among mega-large secondary schools in Region XII.

Recommendations

Anchored to the conclusion drawn in this study, the following are recommended.

1. Mega large schools that are validated SBM Level III may continue to deliver excellent services to their internal and external stakeholders particularly their learners as the main recipient of the services. However, Tacurong City Division had been identified to be rated least among the eight (8) schools divisions in Region XII may conduct SBM benchmarking activities among the SBM Level III schools in South Cotabato Division for technical assistance and best practices.
2. Mega large secondary schools may continue what they have also initiated in service delivery but may give great consideration to the physical plant and facilities, such as the scarcity in the number of classrooms for the teaching and learning process. But, Sultan Kudarat Division rated to the among the eight (8) schools divisions in Region XII may also introduced ideas for benchmarking among schools in Tacurong City Division to adopt some best practices in the implementation of delivery services.
3. Since mega large secondary schools in Region XII have been performing good in the SBM practices, they may still even perform better year after year so they may be able to have autonomy in their budget allocation.
4. Since mega large secondary schools in Region XII have been performing good in their delivery services, they may still even perform better year after year so they may satisfy needs of their clientele for exemplary performance in the satisfaction level.
5. Mega large secondary schools' performance in SBM does not follow a good performance in delivery services or vice versa. Therefore, both programs are independent to one another. Thus, mega large secondary schools may perform good to both programs by identifying which part of the two programs at the least rating in order to formulate and implement remediation or intervention to patch up and even level up the rating.
6. This study may also be conducted to small or even medium school categories to establish significant level of implementation. Thus, finding may help DepEd Division and Regional level to initiate programs or activities that may address the issues and concerns. However, if the researcher wishes to have the same school category, he/she may conduct study on the challenges and successes of SBM implementation through qualitative research.

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